

ASEAN Economic Community (AEC)
A Case Study of Failed Economic Integration
Louangrath, P.I. ★ & Sutanapong, Chanoknath ★★

About the Authors

★Louangrath, P.I. is an Assistant professor in Business Administration at Bangkok University, Thailand. For correspondence, Email: Lecturepedia@gmail.com

★★Chanoknath Sutanapong is an independent researcher. She may be reached by email at: chanoknath.sutanapong@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In 2015, the ASEAN 10 countries launched their economic integration effort called the ASEAN Economic Community (AEC). The purpose of this paper is to assess the effect of that integration four years after its implementation. We used the percentage change of the GDP and percentage change of export volume from 2005 to 2018 as the data. The study divided the data into two periods; ten years before integration and 4 years after integration. In the post-integration period, we are limited to four years because only four years had passed since the AEC integration in 2005. The secondary data was extracted from the IMF's World Economic Outlook Report 2018. The paper employed series of tests to verify the significance of changes in GDP and export growth. The T test for pre- and post-integration shows that there was no significant difference in the GDP growth ($p = 0.7090$), but there was significant reduction in export growth ($p = 0.0047$). For the ASEAN countries, there was a net loss of -0.88 ± 1.36 percentage points in the GDP growth and -1.70 ± 4.33 percentage point in export growth. We concluded that the AEC integration created a net loss for the ASEAN countries. We identified two countries who sustained significant loss in the annual GDP growth: Malaysia ($T = 1.98$; $p = 0.0198$), and Singapore ($T = -2.98$; $p = 0.0004$). No country experienced significant gain in the GDP growth. Statistical test for export growth showed that Malaysia had significant gain in export growth while four countries had significant loss: Brunei ($p = 0.0335$), Laos ($p = 0.0000$), Myanmar ($p = 0.0000$), and Singapore ($p = 0.0065$).

Keyword: AEC, ASEAN, economic integration, economic performance index

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this paper is to examine economic growth in pre- and post-AEC integration. We confine our scope of economic growth to the percentage change in the GDP and export. ASEAN Economic Community (AEC) was launched in 2015 with the purpose of integrating the 10 economies into a common economic community. ASEAN has ten countries; these countries include: Brunei, Cambodia, Indonesia, Laos, Malaysia, Myanmar, Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, and Vietnam. The research issue of this paper is to answer the questions of whether after four years of integration, had there been significant evidence of benefits?

The ASEAN countries had traditionally been divided into two groups. The original ASEAN member nations include Brunei, Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore, and Thailand. The new members include Cambodia, Laos, Myanmar, and Vietnam. The original members had long been known to be more developed than new members. A successful economic integration should eliminate this intra-ASEAN distinction. If the motto: “One Vision, One Identity, One Community” is to mean any thing, the differentiation between the original 6 and new 4 members countries must be eliminated. If one economic community is to be meaningful, the AEC must show some evidence of integration. Economic integration is defined as the creation of a common market where a group of countries unify their separate economies into one common market for purposes of greater economic power and growth. Integration allows member countries greater interaction on the basis of economic, security, political, or social and cultural issues. Economic integration in this sense is synonymous with regional integration. Economic integration is akin to regionalism, such that of NAFTA, to which the AEC may be equated. It is the creation of a new form of organization that co-exists with the old forms (De Lombaerde and Van Langenhove, 2007). The AEC is an integration of 10 economies without losing the individual country's sovereignty.

Existing literature speaks of economic integration in the most favorable light. Pro-integration literature cited the following benefits of economic integration: growth, increase openness and competition, innovation, increase trade, technology transfer, increase investment, and labor mobility. However, the experience of the AEC integration among the 10 ASEAN countries has been nothing but a net loss to all members. Although there is an evidence of “integration,” this evidence leans towards uniform loss of growth. Before the integration, the distinction of the original members and new members had been maintained; however, after integration, all countries shared the same fate of slow growth in export and GDP. Since the integration of the 10 ASEAN countries in 2015, research on the effect of the integration has not been forthcoming. This paper may be one of early assessment attempt of the integration. Note that in Fig. 1, there was a semblance of diversity among the 10 countries from 2005 to 2014. However, from 2015 to 2018, we saw a decline in the GDP growth pattern of all 10 countries.

This research employed 14 years of data. The data is divided into two periods. Before the integration, the data were collected from 2005 to 2014 (Fig. 1, year 1 – 10). The post integration period runs from 2015 to 2018 (Fig. 1, year 11 – 14). The data was sourced from the IMF's annual report on World Economic Outlook 2018 edition. To put the issue of integration in perspective, we also used the competitiveness ranking from the Global Competitiveness Index (GCI) as another source of macroeconomic data.

Fig. 1. Percentage change in GDP during pre- and –post AEC: 2005 – 2018*

*AEC-2015 is at year 11; year 1 = 2005 and year 14 = 2018.

What we observed in the GDP patterns from 2005 to 2018, we also observed in the export growth pattern in the sample period. Although the pattern is less obvious than in the GDP case, percentage change in export volume showed that there is a marked decrease after the integration in 2015. Prior to 2015, the year-to-year percentage change in export growth were high; however, after the integration, this pattern becomes uniform and maintained a consistently lower levels for all ten countries.

The main aim of this paper is to measure the effect of the AEC integration. In so doing, we reviewed five approaches to measuring the effect of economic integration, namely (i) Consumer utility and firm's demand as indicator for integration effect by Peretto (2003), (ii) Degree of openness and connection as indication of integration by Arribas *et al.*, 2006; (iii) Cobb-Douglas production approach to measure the effect of integration by Badinger (2001), (iv) Schumpeterian growth model, and (v) unified growth model.

Our review is not exhaustive, but these three approaches are adequate to put the AEC economic integration into perspective. After reviewing these three approaches, we offer a more simplified approach to measuring the effect of economic integration through the use of statistical tests of pre- and post-changes in macroeconomic indicators.

Fig. 2. Percentage change in export in pre-AEC: 2005 – 2014

This paper is organized into seven sections. In section 1, we introduced the fact that after four years of the AEC integration since 2015, the ASEAN ten countries had not seen positive economic benefits, despite some evidence of group integration. Section 2 provides the theoretical background in economic growth models under the perspective of development economics. Section 3 presents economic integration as one aspect of economic development model. Section 4 presents the data used in this paper. Section 5 presents the findings follows by discussion in section 6. In section 6 we outlined the mutual loss among the ASEAN countries. We offer an index of the effect of economic integration based on the percentage growth of the GDP and export. Lastly, in section 7, we conclude that the AEC integration thus far (2015 – 2018) had produced a net loss for ASEAN.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Economic development theory

There are several theories providing growth models. These theories include (i) Harod-Domar model, (ii) Solow-Swan or exogenous growth model, (iii) endogenous growth theory, (iv) Schumpeterian growth theory, (v) the big push theory, and (vi) unified growth theory. This list is not exhaustive but we will review them in order to put the AEC integration in context of growth theory. We commence our review with the classical model of Harod-Domar.

According to the Keynesian classical theory, economic growth depends on savings and the productivity of capital. The model was called Horod-Domar model (Harod, 1939; Domarm 1946). Similar idea was introduced in 1924 (Cassel, 1967). It is the precursor of exogenous growth model (Hagerman, 2009). The solution to the model was unstable (Scarfe, 1977) and it was later replaced by the Solow-Swan model (Sato, 1964; Solow, 1994). (Appendix 1).

2.1.1 Exogenous growth theory (Solow-Swan Model)

The Solow-Swan growth was also known as exogenous growth theory. According to Solow-Swan, economic growth has been explained by growth theories. The Solow-Swan growth model, for instance, asserts that there is a diminishing return on capital and labor. Labor and capital is depreciated over the years. The amount of new investment is to replace these depreciated valued. This net effect is called a “steady state.” The level of work productivity throughout the world should converge to the same level (Lucas, 1990). The Solow-Swan growth model is called exogenous growth theory. (Appendix 2).

2.1.2 Endogenous growth theory

The endogenous growth theory is another theory used to explain economic growth. Lucas and Romer introduced the endogenous growth theory. According to endogenous growth theory human capital, skills and knowledge contribute to economic growth (Mankiw *et al.*, 1992; Sala-i-Martin *et al.*, 2004; Romer, 1994, 1990). For instance, knowledge in mathematics and science are considered indicative of human capital which may contribute to economic growth (Hanushek and Kimko, 2000). At one time, researchers argued that there is a positive correlation between student mathematic and scientific knowledge and the country's economic growth in less developed countries (Hanushek and Woessmann, 2000, 2001). In more developed economies, there is a lack of correlation between student's test score and economic growth (Breton, 2015). It is cognitive skills, not test score that correlates to economic growth (Hanushek and Woessmann, 2015). (Appendix 3).

2.1.3 Schumpeter's model of creative destruction

Another explanation of economic growth comes from Schumpeter. According to Schumpeter, the creation of new goods and service is a sign of economic growth (Gordon, 2016). Economic growth in Asia had traditionally been contributed to capital investment (Krugman, 1994). The Schumpeterian growth theory asserts that growth resulted from innovation (Landreth, 1976). Growth comes as a result of creative destruction (Aghion; 2002; Carlin and Soskie, 2006), also called the Aghion-Howitt model. Schumpeter's creative destruction is described as:

“The fundamental impulse that sets and keeps the capitalist engine in motion comes from the new consumer's goods, the new methods of production or transportation the new markets,... [This process] incessantly revolutionizes the economic structure from within, incessantly destroying the old one, incessantly creating a new one. This process of Creative Destruction is the essential fact about capitalism.” - Schumpeter (1942; p. 83).

Innovation has the effect of reducing cost (Schleifer, 1986; Corriveau, 1988). Cost reduction increases demand. Increase demand produces growth.

Using Schumpeter's argument as the basis, Aghion and Howitt asserted that “individual innovations are sufficiently important to affect the entire economy.” (Aghion and Howitt, 1992, p. 324). The result of innovation is the destruction existing technology, and creation of new ones. There are two effects that come from innovation: (i) creative destruction, and (ii) general equilibrium, resulted from new level of skilled labor from the innovation. Under this theory, economic growth will happen so long as there are continuing research to create new innovation. When there is an oscillation of research effort in deterministic fashion, i.e. going up and down, not continually increasing, the economic will stop growing due to the “no-growth trap” (*id.*, 325). Growth depends on continuing research and development; R&D efforts in the next period must be higher than the previous one. As soon as the efforts become stationary or less than the prior period, the growth effect will be adversely affected.

This type of growth dependency may not work for all countries. For instance, if a country sees that R&D is more efficient in another country then it will wait for the spillover benefits from another country's innovation instead of engaging in a more costly R&D on its own. Thus, growth in this fashion sometimes is less than optimal (Romer, 1990). However, sometimes instead of the spillover effect, there might be a “business-stealing” effect (Tirole, 1988; p. 399) where the business in one country waits to steal the technology from the true creator. This business-stealing effect hinders innovation in the country. (Appendix 4).

2.1.4 The Big Push Theory (Rosenstein-Rodan Model)

Economic growth is explained by the Big Push Theory. According to the Big Push Theory, a country can move from one developmental stage to the next by large investment in the infrastructure (Murphy *et al.*, 1989). A group of industries acting in concert and move in the same direction could bring a push needed to help the country graduate to the next stage of development (Nath, 1962). This “big push” is made possible by the increased in scale of operation (Mead, 1952). The goal of the Big Push is to achieve industrialization. Rosenstein-Rodan explained:

“Industrialization meant (and still means today) urbanization. What are towns compared with rural zones? They are areas of relatively higher wages. Industrialization proceeded by concentrating in areas of high wages (towns), not in the rural areas. The rich countries were the urban zones and the poorer countries the rural zones of the world economy. That was the reason for the widening gap between developed and underdeveloped countries. The market mechanism alone will not lead to the creation of social overhead capital, which normally accounts for 30 to 35 percent of total investment. That must be sponsored, planned, or programmed (usually by public investment). To take advantage of external economies (due to indivisibilities) required an “optimum” size of enterprises to be brought about by a simultaneous planning of several complementary industries. In the process of development, pecuniary external economies play the same role as technological ones.” (Rosenstein-Rodan, 1984, p. 209; *see also* Scitovsky, 1954).

In describing how the Big Push works, Rosenstein-Rodan wrote:

“There is a minimum level of resources that must be devoted to . . . a development program if it is to have any chance for success. Launching a country into self-sustaining growth is a little like getting an airplane off the ground. There is a critical ground speed which must be passed before the craft can become airborne.” (Rosenstein, 1961: “Notes on the Theory of the ‘Big Push’”).

There are three mechanisms that are used for the Big Push: (i) simultaneous investment in increasing returns in multiple sectors, (ii) multiple equilibria in the economy to switch the economy from cottage equilibria to industrial equilibria, and (iii) shared cost among multiple sectors in investing in the infrastructure (Murphy *et al.*, 1989). The strategy of the Big Push Theory is through: “[t]he movement of machinery and capital towards labor, instead of moving labor towards capital, is the process of industrialization which, together with agrarian improvement, is the most important aspect of the economic development of the depressed areas.” (Rosenstein, 1944; p. 161).

Success of the Big Push theory depends on skilled labor force (Misra and Puri, 2010). In undeveloped economies, price failed to act as signal due to the lack of competition (Scitovsky, 1954). Ideally, if in a perfectly competitive market, if industries acted in concerted, the application of technology in the industry will result in cost reduction (Myint, 1969). This reduction in cost will spill over throughout the industry to lower prices of goods and services and, thus, increase demands (Agarwala and Singh, 1969). As the result, the economy grows. (Appendix 5).

2.1.5 Unified theory of economic growth

Lastly, a more recent development is the unified growth theory. The unified theory of growth is a response to the inconsistency or inadequacy of the exogenous and endogenous growth models. The unified growth theory suggests that:

“... the transition from stagnation to growth is an inevitable outcome of the process of development. The inherent Malthusian interaction between the level of technology and

the size and the composition of the population accelerated the pace of technological progress, and ultimately raised the importance of human capital in the production process. The rise in the demand for human capital in the second phase of industrialization, and its impact on the formation of human capital as well as on the onset of the demographic transition, brought about significant technological advancements along with a reduction in fertility rates and population growth, enabling economies to convert a larger share of the fruits of factor accumulation and technological progress into growth of income per capita, and paving the way for the emergence of sustained economic growth.” (Galor, 173).

UGT is an attempt to explain economic growth in a historical perspective by tracing economic development in the modern state through series of developmental stages, Thus, UGT described economic development as:

“...in early stages of development economies were in the proximity of a stable Malthusian equilibrium. Technology advanced rather slowly, and generated proportional increases in output and population. The inherent positive interaction between population and technology in this epoch, however, gradually increased the pace of technological progress, and due to the delayed adjustment of population, output per capita advanced at a miniscule rate. The slow pace of technological progress in the Malthusian epoch provided a limited scope for human capital in the production process and parents, therefore, had no incentive to reallocate resources towards human capital formation of their offspring.” (Galor, p. 235).

The building blocks of UGT are: (i) Malthusian elements, (ii) forces behind technological progress in the process of development, (iii) origin of human capital formation, and (iv) determination of paternal decisions regarding the quantity and quality of their offspring. The formal argument of UGT is based on the Cobb-Douglas production function. Thus, UGT did not add new things into the literature on development economics, except describing the same issue in a different perspective; in this case, historical perspective. (Appendix 6).

It is against the backdrop of these various growth models that we examine and assess the effect of the AEC integration. Our objective is not to verify which growth theory explains the AEC integration, but we attempt to answer a basic question: “Has the AEC integration produce tangible benefits?” We will measure these benefits in terms of economic growth. In so doing, we use the percentage change in the GDP and export as our unit of analysis.

3.0 ECONOMIC INTEGRATION AS ENGINE FOR GROWTH

As we assess economic integration as an alternative path for economic growth, we are reminded that not all economic development models produced success. We cite one case of a failed economic development theory used in India during that country’s second 5-year plan. That economic development model focuses on domestic consumer market (Feldman, 1964). It was known as Feldman-Mahanalobis Model (Mahanalobis, 1953). The model assumes (i) closed economy; (ii) the economy consists of two sectors: consumption goods sector C and capital goods sector K; (iii) capital goods are non-shiftable; (iv) full capacity production; (v) investment is determined by supply of capital goods; (vi) no changes in prices; (vii) capital is the only scarce factor; and (viii) production of capital goods is independent of the production of consumer good

This model was used in India’s second 5-years plan, and was a subject of great discussion (Bronfenbrenner, 2003). The full capacity output equation for the model was presented by Ghatak:

$$Y_t = Y_0 \left\{ 1 + \alpha_0 \frac{\lambda_k \beta_k + \lambda_c \beta_c}{\lambda_k \beta_k} \left[(1 + \lambda_k \beta_k)^t - 1 \right] \right\}$$

where λ_k is the share of investment in capital goods, λ_c is the share in consumer goods (Ghatak, 2003). According to the model, long run growth depends on long-term investment in capital goods. Since the model emphasizes growth from domestic consumption, problems from increased money supply and inflation caused the Indian government to abandon the model in 1961 (Sen, 1991). It is not the failure of the model that we should appreciate, but the foresight of the Indian government to recognize the failure and has the ability and willingness to turn away from it. Similar foresight should be considered by the ASEAN countries in light of the current predicament of the AEC integration.

3.1 Economic integration as a factor for economic growth

Economic growth due to increase efficiency is called intensive growth. Growth that resulted from increase in input is called extensive growth (Bjork, 1999). The development of new goods and services contributes to economic growth (Gordon (2016). About 80% of growth comes from technology and 20% comes from investment (Krugman, 1994). Much of the benefits of growth came from increase in productivity. Improved productivity had contributed to the decrease in cost. In the 20th century, the real price of goods fell by 90% due to increase in productivity (Rosenberg). That rise in productivity came from technological innovation (Lucas, 1988). With the introduction of technology, the work-week hours were reduced and resulted in the improvement of working condition among workers (Whaples, 1991). Institutional change also contributes to economic growth (Acemoglu and Robinson, 2012). Pro-business law, for instance, is conducive to economic growth (Landes, 1969). Such institutional changes help the states to better manage the nations (Johnson and Koyama, 2017). No one could refute that the rule of law contributes to the betterment of life and economy of the nation (De Soto, 2000).

In this paper we are examining one factor that is a potential contributor to economic growth: economic integration. It is considered an institutional change in line with the growth proposition urged by Acemoglu and Robinson, Johnson and Koyama, and De Soto.

There are two aspects of integration, namely political and economic integrations. In the literature, integration generally includes both. For instance, the working of GATT and its culmination into the creation of the European Community is an example of political and economic integrations. The EU is both a political and economic community. The ASEAN Economic Community is an attempt to have economic integration without political integration. Due to its intra-group diversity in political institutions, infrastructure and historical development, it seemed logical that an attempt to affect political integration, like that found in the EU, would inevitably fail; thus, only economic integration may be possible. The AEC's model is akin to the North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA) where political integration is not the aim. In NAFTA, the US, Canada and Mexico integrated their markets, but each country retains its own political sovereignty.

3.2 Combined political and economic integration

Integration generally entails both political and economic integration. The argument in favor of political integration is that it contributes to competition and innovation in the integrated economy. Political integration has a positive market size effect, but a negative on trade openness (Spolaore and Wacziarg, 2005). Economic integration has positive effect on growth and increasing competition in economic markets (Peretto, 2003; Grossman and Helpman, 1991). By accepting these two arguments, integrationists urged both political and economic integrations. The support for growth through integration is openness. The effects of country size on growth are less important as economies become more open (Alesina *et al.*, 2000; 2005); country size would not be an issue if there is an accompanied political integration. For instance, Brou and Ruta (2007) wrote that:

“Political integration makes the competition for transfers more intense. Firms must increase their rent seeking effort in order to maintain their share of government transfers. As profits from the political market fall, each firm must rely more on the economic market for profits. This makes competition in the economic market more intense and increases the incentive to innovate. At the same time, higher costs of rent seeking drive some local firms out of the market. This has the effect of reducing the number of firms competing in the economic market, which reduces the incentive to innovate. Overall, the effect of political integration on innovation, growth and welfare is ambiguous.” – Brou and Ruta, 2007; p. 3.

However, in the case of AEC integration, only economic integration is targeted. Traditionally, the ASEAN countries followed a policy of political independence and the principle of noninterference; each member country refrained from interfering in another country’s internal politics. Thus, the obvious question is “can regional integration succeed if only economic integration is implemented, without political integration?”

3.3 Economic integration without political integration

The AEC is not an exceptional case in economic integration without political integration. NAFTA, for instance, is an integration that dispenses with political integration. The AEC is an attempt to create economic and cultural communities without political integration. The common rationale for economic integration is the idea of economies of scale derived from economic integration (O’Sullivan and Sheffrin, 2003). The argument is that one country alone could do less efficiently than a group of nations acting in consonant. This is called economies of scale of public goods by means of economic integration.

Although efficiency in external trade may be achieved, it comes at the cost of losing some degrees of political sovereignty. Adherents of advocacy of economic integration include: Milanovic (1996), Alesina and Spolaore (1997), Bolton and Roland (1997), Casella and Feinstein (2002) and Alesina *et al.*, (2005).

Economic integration is presented in 5 stages: (i) free exchange area, (ii) customs union, (iii) common market, (iv) economic union, (v) economic and monetary union (Balassa, 1961). Viner’s concept of custom unions as one of a number of arrangements for reducing tariff barriers between political units while maintaining barriers against imports from outside regions (Viner, 1937). The effect of customs union is trade diversion and trade creation. Haebler described trade union as:

“A customs union must be especially advantageous for small States, since these are particularly injured if they exclude one another’s goods. We must emphasise that the economic advantages of a customs union can be proved only by exact Free Trade reasoning as to the international division of labour and the Theory of Comparative Cost, and not by any reference to racial, cultural, and other relations. From an economic standpoint a general removal of duties by the States would be better than a removal of duties only between themselves retaining their duties against other countries.” Gottfried von Haebler (1936), *The Theory of International Trade*, pp.390.

Haebler’s description includes free-trade area, a customs union, a common market, an economic union and complete economic integration (Balassa, p. 176). The question is what is the effect of the integration? (Balassa, 1961; p. 177).

The economic effect of integration may include “integration-induced technology-led growth” and “integration-induced investment-led growth” (Baldwin and Seghezza, 1996). The economic integration intends to break down barriers. Barriers are hinderances to trade. These

hindrances include language, colonial past, military or political relations, currencies, or trade agreements on trade tariffs (Brahmbhatt, 1998; Frankel, 2000; Knetter and Slaughter, 1999).

The indicators of the effect of integration include: (i) openness. (ii) balanced relationship, (iii) indirect relationship, and (iv) sizes. In this paper, we will not measure these five factors. In an attempt to answer the question of what had been the effect of the AEC integration in the past four years, we look at two indicators: annual percentage change in the GDP and export volume.

3.4 Modeling the effect of economic integration

3.4.1 Consumer utility and firm's demand as indicator for integration effect

In this part of the literature review, we examined the formal argument presented by Peretto (2003), Brou and Ruta (2007) and their progeny. At the end of this review of the formal arguments and models, we will reject them as impracticable and not reflective of all cases of economic integration. In place of these formal arguments, we will present a more simplified measure of the effect of economic integration by introducing two factors as indicators of the effect of economic integration: *percentage change in the GDP and export volume*. We are mindful of the fact that Peretto, Brou and Ruta, and other analyzed the effect of economic integration in the context of the more developed economies in the West. Even the latest experiment of NAFTA, as a recent example of economic integration without political union, may be generalized under Peretto's argument; however, the case of ASEAN Economic Community (AEC) does not have the equivalent basic developmental preconditions. The ten economies of ASEAN are mixed bag of developed, developing, and undeveloped economies. Thus, the experience of the AEC may not follow the predicted patterns of "benefits" foresaw by Peretto and subsequent studies in the same line of argument. Nevertheless, we present their formal arguments and models in our literature review so that the AEC integration may be seen in its rightful theoretical perspective. It is in such light and context that we could better evaluate the AEC four years after its implementation (from 2015 to 2018).

Peretto presented the argument and model for the effect of economic integration in series of elegant mathematical models. We summarized Peretto's formal argument and models in the following statements (1) – (8). Peretto, like many economists writing on economic integration, tend to focus on consumers and firm as the starting point. This bottom-up approach started in a predictable and logical pattern of presentation. Consumer's utility and firm's demand prior to the integration are contrasted with those after the integration under the condition of with tariff (prior to integration) and without tariff (after integration). We will trace these steps.

Consumer index is given by:

$$C = \left[\sum C_i^{\epsilon-1/\epsilon} \right]^{\epsilon/\epsilon-1} \quad (1)$$

where $\epsilon > 1$ is the elasticity of product substitution, C_i is consumer purchase of different goods, N is the number of goods.

As the economies integrate, more technology will be made available in one common market. As the result, labor productivity will rise. Labor productivity rises with the rise of accumulated technology:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{Z}_t &= L_{Z_i} K_i \\ K &= Z_i + \sum_{j \neq i}^N \frac{\gamma}{1 + \delta(N+1)} Z_j \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $0 \leq \gamma \leq 1$, Z_i is the new knowledge generated in the time interval t after integration dt by allocating labor LZ_i units to R&D, γ is the fraction of knowledge that becomes public, and δ is the speed of congestion of increasing return.

With the above preliminaries, Peretto then presented trade model with and without tariffs. The trade model with tariffs, i.e. prior to integration, has the following defined terms: c = countries,

N_k = domestic firms in k countries; $M = \sum_{k=1}^c N_k$ is the global number of firms, and τ = tariffs.

Now, the new consumer index and demand may be presented:

$$C_k = \left[\sum_{i=1}^{N_k} C_{ik}^{\epsilon-1/\epsilon} + \sum_{s \neq k}^c \sum_{i=1}^{N_s} C_{is}^{\epsilon-1/\epsilon} \right]^{\epsilon/\epsilon-1} \quad (3)$$

C_k implies that in an integrated economy, a typical consumer prefers all goods regardless of whether the goods are offered by domestic or foreign firms. The demand for the firm in the integrated economy is:

$$K_{ik} = Z_{ik} + \sum_{j \neq i}^{N_k} \frac{\gamma}{1 + \delta(N-1)} Z_{jk} + \sum_{s=k}^c \sum_{j=1}^{N_s} \frac{\gamma}{1 + \delta(N+1)} Z_j \quad (4)$$

K_{ik} implies that in an integrated economy, the demand for domestic firm is a spillover from the global population of firms.

In country k , consumers maximize C_k subject to:

$$E_k \left[\sum_{i=1}^{N_k} P_{ik} C_{ik} + \sum_{s \neq k}^c \sum_{j=1}^{N_s} (1 + \tau)^{1-\epsilon} P_{js}^{1-\epsilon} \right]^{1/1-\epsilon} \quad (5)$$

The consumer demand for i product from domestic firm is:

$$C_{ik}^D = E_k \frac{P_{ik}^{-\epsilon}}{P_k^{1-\epsilon}} \quad (6)$$

The demand for i products imported from another country. Thus, the demand by firm i in country k is:

$$X_{ik} = X_{ik}^D + X_{ik}^F = LE_k \frac{P_{ik}^{-\epsilon}}{P_k^{1-\epsilon}} + LE_s \frac{(1 + \tau) P_{ik}^{-\epsilon}}{P_s^{1-\epsilon}} \quad (7)$$

where X_{ik}^D and X_{ik}^F are firm's domestic and foreign sales, respectively. The superscript D stands for domestic and F stands for foreign. The term P_s is the price index for consumer goods in country s . The price elasticity of (7) is given by:

$$\xi = \epsilon - (\epsilon - 1) \frac{1 + (1 + \tau)^{1-2\epsilon}(c-1)}{1 + (1 + \tau)^\epsilon(c-1)} \frac{c}{1 + (c-1)(1 + \tau)^{1-\epsilon}} \frac{1}{cN} \quad (8)$$

Equations (1) to (8) serve as the foundational materials for the argument that trade in integrated and nonintegrated markets are unequal. Thus far, the argument is logical, but what follow does not reflect the real world as the model begins to contrast *autarky* and *free trade*. Autarky is an extreme case. Integration analysis is not contrasting integrated economy with extreme case of non-trade of autarky for such condition does not exist in normal circumstances. The ASEAN, for instance, instead of acting in consonant as in AEC, had each country pursued its own independent trade policy. Firms in such countries succeed through their own efforts. However, with integration, firms' efforts may be more organized or targeted. Marketing cost may be reduced as a benefit of integration. Integration analysis is about comparing independent trade policies in un-integrated economies with the unified policy in integrated economies.

Peretto outlined autarky condition by looking at the number of firms and cost reduction effect. In autarky, the number of firms is given by:

$$\phi = \frac{L}{\xi N} [1 - \theta(\xi - 1)] + \frac{\rho}{\alpha} \quad (NN_{autarky})$$

The cost structure is:

$$g = \theta \frac{1}{\rho} \left[\frac{1}{\xi - 1} \log N + \log \frac{\xi - 1}{\xi} + \frac{\theta \phi \theta(\xi - 1) \alpha - \rho}{\rho (1 - \theta(\xi - 1))} \right] \quad GG_{autarky}$$

where price elasticity of demand is defined by $\xi = \frac{\epsilon(N-1)+1}{N}$ and the productivity of R&D is

given by: $\alpha = \frac{1 + (\gamma + \delta)(N-1)}{1 + \delta(N-1)}$ (Peretto, p. 190). The welfare under autarky is given by

($UU_{autarky}$):

$$U = \frac{1}{\rho} \log N + \log \frac{\xi - 1}{\xi} + \frac{\theta \phi \theta(\xi - 1) \alpha - \rho}{\rho (1 - \theta(\xi - 1))} \quad (UU_{autarky})$$

In contrast, Peretto presented the free trade condition as:

$$\phi = \frac{L}{N} \frac{1 - \theta[\xi(cN) - 1]}{\xi(cN)} + \frac{\rho}{\alpha(cN)} \quad (NN_{trade})$$

NN_{trade} represents the number of firms in each country at general equilibrium of global economy where the global industry is in systematic Nash equilibrium with free entry and exit. R&D productivity measure is: $\alpha = \frac{1 + (\gamma + \delta)(cN-1)}{1 + \delta(cN-1)}$. The rate of cost reduction as the result of open trade is given by:

$$g = \theta \frac{\phi \theta(\xi - 1) \alpha - \rho}{1 - \theta(\xi - 1)} \quad (GG_{trade})$$

The welfare under open trade is given by:

$$U = \frac{1}{\rho} \left[\log(cN)^{\epsilon/\epsilon-1} + \log \left(\frac{\xi-1}{\xi} \frac{1}{cN} \right) + \frac{g}{\rho} \right]$$

By substituting (GG_{trade}), the general welfare is obtained by:

$$U = \frac{1}{\rho} \left[\frac{1}{\epsilon-1} \log(cN) + \log \frac{\xi-1}{\xi} \frac{\theta}{\rho} \frac{\phi\theta(\xi-1)\alpha - \rho}{1-\theta(\xi-1)} \right] \quad (UU_{trade})$$

The analysis is to compare (GG_{trade}) and (UU_{trade}) to $GG_{autarky}$ and ($UU_{autarky}$), the net effect is that the number of firms in free trade is larger than that in autarky, and the utility level in free trade is also higher than that in autarky.

At this point, we pose a simple question: *What if the number of firms under free trade increases, but the welfare does not?* This is the case of the AEC integration. If the number of firms increases, but the welfare of the people (consumers), as measured by the rate of growth of the GDP, does not follow at the same rate, we must also for alternative model to help explain the AEC's experience.

3.4.2 Degree of openness and connection as indication of integration

One approach offered the measure of integration by looking at the following factors: openness, balanced relationship, indirect relationship, and size (Arribas *et al.*, 2006, p. 4). Arribas *et al.* provided a formal argument for the degree of integration as follows:

$$DI_i = \sqrt{DO_i(DTC_i)} \quad (9)$$

where $DO_i = \sum_{j \in N} DO_{ij} = \frac{\sum_{j \in N} X_{ij}}{\hat{Y}_i}$ and $DTC_i = \frac{\sum_{j \in N} \alpha_{ij}^{\infty} \beta_{ij}^{\infty}}{\sqrt{\sum_{j \in N} (\alpha_{ij}^{\infty})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{j \in N} (\beta_{ij}^{\infty})^2}}$. Other elements

are defined as: N = set of nodes of economies; g = number of elements in N , i.e. countries; X_{ij} = flow from economy I to j ; Y_i = activity volume or size of economy, i.e. GDP; $\hat{Y}_i = Y_i - \alpha_i Y_i$ is the production destined for export; $\alpha_i = \frac{Y_i}{\sum_{j \in N} Y_j}$ is the relative weight of economy I to the world

economy (Arribas *et al.*, pp. 4 – 9). This argument asserts that the degree of integration is determined by the degree of openness (DO) and the degree of total connection (DTC).

We find this approach not effective as a measure of the effect of economic integration. The degrees of openness and connection between economies do not tell us the level of change after the integration. For instance, this approach cannot answer the question of how has consumer utility, firm demand or net trade volume or percentage change in the GDP been affected by the economic integration? Thus, the question of “degree of integration” or the index of integration is not a useful measure. It may have an academic value, but lacks the practical value. One main issue in analyzing economic integration is “what are the benefits from integration?”

3.4.3 Cobb-Douglas production function approach to measure the effect of integration

We present another approach to explain for the anticipated benefits from economic integration by Badinger (2001). Badinger's approach relied on the endogenous growth factor of the Cobb-Douglas production function (Cobb and Douglas, 1928) with constant return to scale: $Y = AK^\alpha L^{1-\alpha}$ (Silberberg and Suen, 2001) or simply $Y = AK^\alpha$. This approach is classified as microeconomic approach (Filipe and Adams, 2005). It is written in a log-difference format, Badinger's argument follows:

$$\Delta \ln Y_t = \Delta \ln A_t + \alpha \Delta \ln K_t \quad (10)$$

where $y = Y/L$ is the GDP per employee; A is the total factor of production; and $K = K/L$ is the physical capital per employee. For trans-log conversion of the Cobb-Douglas function, see (Berndt and Christensen, 1973; Wynn and Holden, 1974). The Cobb-Douglas approach uses the measure of productivity as the unit of analysis (Douglas, 1976). According to Badinger, growth comes from two sources stemming from integration: investment and technology. For integration investment-led growth, there are two competing hypotheses:

$$\Delta \ln A_t = \delta_{1A} + \varphi_{1A} INT_t \quad (11a)$$

$$\Delta \ln A_t = \delta_{2A} + \varphi_{2A} \Delta INT_t \quad (12b)$$

For integration technology-led growth, there are also two competing hypotheses:

$$\Delta \ln K_t = \delta_{1k} + \varphi_{1k} INT_t \quad (13a)$$

$$\Delta \ln K_t = \delta_{2k} + \varphi_{2k} \Delta INT_t \quad (13b)$$

The argument from (10) to (14b) (Badinger, pp. 6-14) are the clarification of what Baldwin and Seghezza (1996) described the *permanent effect* that led to the steeper slope of the growth path. Both Badinger and Baldwin had accurately described the experience of Europe's integration effort under GATT and its later day of the EU. In this paper, we asked whether the so-called permanent effect of integration investment-led and integration technology-led growths could result in the AEC integration among the 10 ASEAN countries? The empirical evidence in Figs. 1 and 2 suggests that the EU experience was not repeated in the AEC.

Both Arribas *et al.* and Badinger presented valid arguments in favor of economic integration. However, neither could explain the experience of the AEC integration since 2015. Where Badinger hypothesized that there would be technology-led and investment-led growth from integration, the AEC produced neither. Where Arribas *et al.* expected to see the economies becoming more integrated, there is an evidence of integration in a slow growth direction.

In this paper, we offer a more simplified view of the degree of integration in the context of the AEC. Using the ASEAN Economic Community (AEC) as the proxy to illustrate our proposed measurement of integration, we employ the percentage growth in the GDP and the percentage growth in export volume as the indicators for integration. To which we offered the following propositions: (i) prior to integration, countries would manifest diversity in GDP and export growth rates, (ii) after integration, the diversity among member countries' export and GDP growth rates will be narrower; and (iii) there are three possible effects of integration, namely no change, loss, or gain.

Using the ASEAN countries as a group proxy to explain the rationale for the above three propositions, we assert that (a) the diversity in proposition 1 may be attributed to the diversity in economic, political and historical development or factor endowment of the countries; (b) the diversity is expected to be narrower after integration due to common policy affecting trade, i.e. removal of trade barriers and common trade policy; and (c) the effects of integration depends on

how the economic integration is implemented. If the removal of tariffs is not accompanied by increase in trade volume, the government's loss in revenue could not be adequately compensated, or if the increase in trade volume is due to free trade arrangement with larger trading partners where trade terms are unequal with net imports contributed to declining trade term, then the net effect of integration may be negative and vice versa or no change depending on the trade term condition subsequent to the integration. We relied on empirical evidence in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 to support our three propositions and explanations.

4.0 DATA AND METHODOLOGY

This paper used secondary data. The data was extracted from the IMF's annual report of World Economic Outlook 2017. ASEAN's common market called ASEAN Economic Community (AEC) was launched in 2015. We tracked the group's GDP and export patterns 10 years before the integration: 2005 – 2014, and compared them to those from 2015 to 2018.

Ten years prior to the AEC integration (2005 – 2014), the percentage change of the GDP for the ten ASEAN countries ranged from the low of 0.38 (Brunei) to the high of 8.21 (Myanmar). As a group, the 10 years mean for the GDP percentage change was 5.68 ± 2.32 . The country GDP change from 2005 to 2014 is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Percentage change in GDP during pre-AEC: 2005 – 2014

Year	1*	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
2005	0.39	13.25	5.69	6.94	3.27	13.57	4.78	7.49	4.19	7.55
2006	4.41	0.77	5.50	8.95	4.70	3.08	5.24	8.86	4.97	6.98
2007	0.12	0.21	6.35	7.85	9.60	1.99	6.62	9.11	5.44	7.13
2008	(1.98)	6.69	7.44	7.82	7.64	3.60	4.15	1.79	1.73	5.66
2009	(1.82)	0.09	4.70	7.37	8.33	5.14	1.15	(0.60)	(0.69)	5.40
2010	2.65	5.96	6.38	8.02	6.87	5.35	7.63	15.24	7.51	6.42
2011	3.74	7.18	6.17	7.99	4.85	5.59	3.66	6.35	0.84	6.24
2012	0.91	7.26	6.03	7.81	1.89	7.33	6.68	4.08	7.24	5.25
2013	2.13)	7.44	5.56	8.03	5.20	8.43	7.06	5.11	2.69	5.42
2014	(2.51)	7.07	5.01	7.61	5.70	7.99	6.15	3.88	0.98	5.98
Mean	0.38	7.59	5.88	7.84	5.81	8.21	5.31	6.13	3.49	6.20
n	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
SD	2.54	3.49	0.78	0.52	2.35	3.55	1.96	4.42	2.81	0.80
T	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83
μ	(1.09)	5.58	5.43	7.54	4.45	6.15	4.18	3.57	1.86	5.74
σ	2.82	3.87	0.86	0.57	2.60	3.93	2.17	4.90	3.12	0.89
pValue**	0.01	0.21	0.47	0.18	0.48	0.14	0.56	0.42	0.83	0.41

*ASEAN 10 countries: 1. Brunei, 2. Cambodia, 3. Indonesia, 4. Laos, 5. Malaysia, 6. Myanmar, 7. Philippines, 8. Singapore, 9. Thailand, and 10. Vietnam. **pValue in relations to group: 5.68 ± 2.32 .

The integration occurred in 2015, four years after integration had shown a decrease in the growth of the ASEAN's GDP. The argument in favor of integration asserts that integration will result in the increase of the GDP, i.e. through investment-led or technology-led growth; the percentage change in the GDP with show a positive increase. If we run the time series in the linear form $Y = a + bX$, the slope of the line would be positive: $b > 0$. Brunei changed from 0.38 to -0.33 and Myanmar changed from 8.21 to 6.62. The overall picture for the group does not look promising. The mean for the GDP change in ASEAN after AEC integration for the period 2015 – 2018 is 4.80 ± 2.45 ; there has been a loss of about one percentage point ($5.68 - 4.80 = 0.88$).

Table 2. Percentage change in GDP during post-AEC: 2015 – 2018

Year	1*	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
2015	(0.41)	7.20	4.88	7.27	2.95	6.99	6.07	2.24	3.02	6.68
2016	(2.47)	7.04	5.03	7.02	2.27	5.87	6.92	2.40	3.28	6.21
2017	0.55	6.95	5.07	6.83	4.00	6.72	6.67	3.62	3.90	6.81
2018	0.99	6.90	5.30	6.81	3.50	6.90	6.67	2.94	3.87	6.60
Mean	(0.33)	7.02	5.07	6.98	3.18	6.62	6.58	2.80	3.52	6.58
n	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
SD	1.54	0.13	0.18	0.21	0.74	0.51	0.36	0.62	0.44	0.26
T	2.35	2.35	2.35	2.35	2.35	2.35	2.35	2.35	2.35	2.35
μ	(2.14)	6.87	4.86	6.73	2.31	6.02	6.16	2.07	3.00	6.27
σ	2.19	0.19	0.25	0.30	1.06	0.73	0.52	0.89	0.62	0.37
pValue**	0.02	0.18	0.46	0.19	0.25	0.23	0.23	0.21	0.30	0.23

*ASEAN 10 countries: 1. Brunei, 2. Cambodia, 3. Indonesia, 4. Laos, 5. Malaysia, 6. Myanmar, 7. Philippines, 8. Singapore, 9. Thailand, and 10. Vietnam. **pValue in relations to group: 4.80 ± 2.45 .

Export is used as an indicator of benefits or loss in accessing the AEC integration. The argument in favor of economic integration asserts that integration will produce more trade. Trade consists of import and export; in this paper, we used net trade data as the indicator for the effect of integration on trade. If the net trade increases, it means that integration produces an increase in export. If net trade decrease, it may mean that import increases. An increase in import may explain a general decrease in net trade. The general picture of export earning for the ten countries in ASEAN, measured by the percentage change, over the ten years period (2004 – 2015) prior to the AEC integration is presented in Fig. 2.

The raw data for the pre-AEC integration is presented in Table 3. Brunei has the lowest percentage change in export (-1.47) and Myanmar was the highest export earner as measured by percentage change (13.35). The average for the ASEAN group in this pre-AEC integration period was 6.88 ± 5.29 .

Table 3. Percentage change in export during pre-AEC: 2005 – 2014

Year	1*	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
2005	(1.26)	8.77	11.89	11.73	5.78	15.62	0.99	12.50	7.76	5.95
2006	4.42	18.77	4.52	14.42	6.91	39.45	16.81	11.15	10.79	14.30
2007	(9.1)	(3.06)	(3.18)	7.56	(3.85)	15.84	7.00	8.60	8.89	13.31
2008	(7.05)	2.18	(2.95)	13.66	(7.30)	0.01	(2.21)	4.84	6.26	2.13
2009	(6.66)	(4.96)	5.61	4.88	(10.47)	12.89	(5.87)	(7.66)	(12.14)	3.74
2010	11.71	33.85	3.43	16.73	3.62	10.30	19.86	17.44	14.22	6.58
2011	(4.58)	15.85	6.69	21.67	6.26	9.63	(0.69)	6.67	9.51	4.13
2012	(2.80)	25.98	1.85	6.69	(6.49)	4.86	15.97	1.70	4.88	15.59
2013	(9.28)	16.35	3.05	10.62	0.07	15.36	3.72	5.95	2.72	16.94
2014	4.32	13.85	1.63	22.08	6.50	9.49	11.52	3.36	0.26	10.98
Mean	(1.47)	12.76	3.25	13.00	0.10	13.35	6.71	6.46	5.32	9.37
n	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
SD	7.07	12.34	4.45	5.93	6.63	10.46	8.93	6.82	7.33	5.47
T	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83
μ	(5.56)	5.61	0.68	9.57	(3.73)	7.29	1.54	2.51	1.07	6.20
σ	7.84	13.69	4.93	6.58	7.35	11.60	9.91	7.56	8.13	6.07
pValue**	0.06	0.13	0.25	0.12	0.10	0.49	0.47	0.38	0.38	0.32

*ASEAN 10 countries: 1. Brunei, 2. Cambodia, 3. Indonesia, 4. Laos, 5. Malaysia, 6. Myanmar, 7. Philippines, 8. Singapore, 9. Thailand, and 10. Vietnam. **pValue in relations to group: 6.89 ± 5.29

Similar to the pre-integration GDP, the percentage change in export in the post-integration period (2005 – 2018) showed that Brunei went from -1.47 to -3.91 and the ASEAN export champion, Myanmar, went from 13.35 to 5.77 or a loss of 7.58 percentage points in export growth. For the ASEAN group, the average annual percentage growth of export was 6.89 ± 5.29 prior to integration; this value dropped to 5.18 ± 4.73 after integration.

Table 4. Percentage change in export during post-AEC: 2015 – 2018

Year	1*	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
2015	(13.77)	12.64	0.08	(4.80)	4.05	(0.11)	0.44	4.74	1.57	9.77
2016	(1.89)	14.51	(0.69)	10.53	3.63	3.44	4.99	1.11	2.79	10.74
2017	(1.98)	10.83	5.56	6.10	8.22	17.18	11.38	4.10	6.59	15.85
2018	2.02	11.20	6.22	2.28	3.88	2.57	10.41	3.96	3.99	13.10
Mean	(3.91)	12.30	2.79	3.53	4.95	5.77	6.81	3.48	3.74	12.37
n	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00
SD	6.84	1.67	3.60	6.50	2.19	7.76	5.09	1.61	2.14	2.71
T	2.35	2.35	2.35	2.35	2.35	2.35	2.35	2.35	2.35	2.35
μ	11.94)	0.33	1.44)	(4.10)	2.37	(3.34)	0.82	1.58	1.22	9.18
σ	9.74	2.38	5.13	9.25	3.12	11.05	7.25	2.30	3.05	3.86
pValue**	0.26	0.07	0.31	0.36	0.48	0.45	0.37	0.36	0.38	0.06

*ASEAN 10 countries: 1. Brunei, 2. Cambodia, 3. Indonesia, 4. Laos, 5. Malaysia, 6. Myanmar, 7. Philippines, 8. Singapore, 9. Thailand, and 10. Vietnam. **pValue in relations to group: 5.18 ± 4.73 .

5.0 FINDINGS

5.1 Selecting appropriate testing protocol

We examined the net gain of GDP and export growth in a year-to-year basis during pre- and post-integration. This examination was accomplished in two steps. First, we look at country-by-country change and then we looked at the ASEAN as a group in the pre- and post-integration period.

We note that the group's effect size under the Cohen's *d* measure is low. The effect size for the percentage change in GDP is 0.33 and 0.37 for export. However, despite low group effect size, per country effect size showed that five countries had positive large effect size on their GDP; these countries include: Indonesia (1.20), Laos (1.86), Malaysia (1.27), and Singapore (0.87). For export, two countries showed large effect size: Laos (1.56), and Malaysia (-0.83).

The use of effect size had been advocated by many researchers; the APA, for instance, insisted that:

“Always present effect sizes for primary outcomes...If the units of measurement are meaningful on a practical level (e.g., number of cigarettes smoked per day), then we usually prefer an unstandardized measure (regression coefficient or mean difference) to a standardized measure (*r* or *d*).” — L. Wilkinson and APA Task Force on Statistical Inference (1999, p. 599).

Although there are several effect size measurement methods, i.e. correlation (Cohen, 1992; Olejnik, 2003; and Steiger, 2004) and difference families (Hedges and Olkin, 1985; Hedges, 1981) of effect size, we found them inadequate. The Cohen's *d* employs the same method as the standard score equation, but differed in using the pool standard deviation instead of sample standard deviation. Even so, the result is an incomplete calculation since a standard score calculation must be followed by the reading of the percentage probability: *F*(*Z*) from which the pValue may be calculated as $1 - F(Z)$. If these later steps are followed, the evaluation scale of Cohen *d* reading would break down. According to the Cohen's and Sawilowsky's table on effect size, 0.80 is considered large (Cohen, 1988; p. 67; Sawilowsky, 2009); however, under the *Z* score equation

0.80 would produce $F(Z) = 0.7882$ and $p\text{Value} = 0.2118$. Due to such weakness, we opted for the T test to measure the pre- and post-integration by:

$$T = \frac{(\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2) - (\mu_1 - \mu_2)}{S \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2}}} \quad (14)$$

$$\text{where } S = \sqrt{\frac{(n_1 - 1)SE_1^2 + (n_2 - 1)SE_2^2}{n_1 + n_2 - 2}}$$

5.2 Net change of percentage GDP growth from AEC integration

In measuring the effect of economic integration, we divide the countries into two categories: losers and winners. Winner countries are those that made significant gain in percentage change in the GDP; losers are those who made significant loss in the percentage change in the GDP. Under the 95% confidence interval, no country had made significant gain from the integration. If the confidence interval is lowered to 90%, two countries (Cambodia ($p = 0.0636$) and Singapore ($p = 0.0903$)) made significant gain in percentage change in the GDP growth.

Note that the significance measurement obtained through the T test is more informing than the Cohen's d effect size measurement. Under the effect size measurement, four countries experience "large" effect in the percentage change in the GDP as the result of the AEC integration. However, when the significance is used with well defined confidence interval, only two countries had significant change under 90% CI, but not significant at 95%.

Table 5: Before and After AEC Integration effect on GDP and export % growth

%Δ	1*	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
GDP Pre	0.38	7.59	5.88	7.84	5.81	8.21	5.31	6.13	3.49	6.20
GDP Post	(0.33)	7.02	5.07	6.98	3.18	6.62	6.58	2.80	3.52	6.58
GDP Net	(0.71)	(0.57)	(0.81)	(0.86)	(2.63)	(1.59)	1.27	(3.33)	0.03	0.38
Effect size: d	0.31	0.19	1.20	1.86	1.27	0.51	(0.75)	0.87	(0.01)	(0.53)
T test pValue	(0.27)	1.53	0.28	0.06	0.42	1.15	0.64	1.37	0.93	0.18
	0.2910	0.0636	0.4673	0.4322	0.4041	0.1392	0.3100	0.0903	0.2033	0.4846

*ASEAN 10 countries: 1. Brunei, 2. Cambodia, 3. Indonesia, 4. Laos, 5. Malaysia, 6. Myanmar, 7. Philippines, 8. Singapore, 9. Thailand, and 10. Vietnam.

The net change in the percentage change in the GDP is illustrated pictorially by Fig. 3. Note that only three countries experienced a net gain (Philippines (+1.27), Thailand (+0.03) and Vietnam (+0.38)). These values are obtained by using the ten years mean of pre-integration period less the four years mean of the post-integration. Eight countries had their means GDP growth dropped after the AEC integration.

At a glance, the AEC integration does not deliver what it had promised. As an economic community that is committed to regulatory harmonization, removal of tariffs, labor migration, and free flow of capital, one expects that the post-integration GDP for all members would change in a positive direction. However, empirical evidence points to an opposite direction. The evidence from the past four years showed that the AEC has failed.

If the GDP is any indication of the standard of living, a decrease in the percentage growth of the GDP presents a poor prospect for economic prosperity. The GDP measures presented in Table 5

and Fig. 3 are percentage change from year to year, not the actual GDP growth. The percentage change is used as the unit of analysis because it provides a clearer picture than the actual per capita GDP amount.

Fig. 3. Net GDP gain as annual percentage growth comparing 10 years prior to 4 years after AEC integration (2005 – 2018)

5.3 Net change of percentage export growth from AEC integration

Export had been seen as the engine for growth among the ASEAN countries CITE. We examined the export growth pattern for 10 years prior to the AEC integration and compared it to the four years post-integration. There are four countries which show significant decrease in export: Brunei, Indonesia, Laos, and Myanmar. Only one country experience significant net gain in percentage export growth: Cambodia. The remaining five countries (Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, and Vietnam) showed some gains, but those gains are not significant (Table 6).

Table 6: Before and After AEC Integration effect on export and export % growth

%Δ	1*	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Export Pre	(1.47)	2.76	3.25	13.00	0.10	13.35	6.71	6.46	5.32	9.37
Export Post	(3.91)	12.30	2.79	3.53	4.95	5.77	6.81	3.48	3.74	12.37
Export Net	(2.44)	(0.46)	(0.46)	(9.47)	4.85	(7.58)	0.10	(2.98)	(1.58)	3.00
Effect size: <i>d</i>	0.35	0.04	0.11	1.56	(0.83)	0.77	(0.01)	0.50	0.25	(0.61)
T test pValue	(2.42)	3.01	(1.16)	(2.68)	0.83	(1.73)	(0.48)	1.36	1.11	(0.01)
	0.0009	0.0004	0.0057	0.0002	0.2375	0.0119	0.2141	0.0922	0.1498	0.4008

*ASEAN 10 countries: 1. Brunei, 2. Cambodia, 3. Indonesia, 4. Laos, 5. Malaysia, 6. Myanmar, 7. Philippines, 8. Singapore, 9. Thailand, and 10. Vietnam

What the test static lacks, the visual effect for the net change of the integration provides the shocking picture in Fig. 4. Only two countries showed gains in percentage change in the export growth. The remaining eight countries lost their export growth momentum after the AEC

integration. The scope of this paper is to measure the change and the net gain or loss of the integration, the reasons or causation for the loss of the export growth is another sub-issue worth pursuing.

Fig. 4. Net export gain as annual percentage growth comparing 10 years prior to 4 years after AEC integration (2005 – 2018)

6.0 DISCUSSION

6.1 AEC integration did not help optimize utility

The empirical findings of this study contradict the general argument in favor of economic integration which asserts that:

“...integration raises growth and welfare because exit of domestic firms is more than compensated by entry of foreign firms. In other words, the fact that domestic consumers and producers gain access to foreign goods and knowledge means that integration generates a larger, more competitive market where firms have access to a more diverse body of technological spillovers that supports faster growth. The growth effect is larger the less competitive the economy is before integration, while it is negligible for economies that are very competitive to begin with. The effects of a gradual reduction of barriers to trade.” (Peretto, 2003, p. 178).

We accept Peretto’s argument that a “typical consumer maximizes life time utility” by:

$$U(t) = \int_t^{\infty} e^{-\rho(\tau-t)} \log C(\tau) d\tau \quad (15)$$

where $\rho > 0$ subject to budget constraint and initial wealth:

$$\int_t^{\infty} e^{-A} E(\tau) d\tau \leq \int_t^{\infty} e^{-A} W(\tau) d\tau + B(t) \quad (16)$$

where $A = \int_t^{\tau} r(s) ds$, ρ = individual discount rate; E = per capita consumption expenditure, B = individual assets, $W \equiv 1$ is wage rate and C is consumption defined by:

$$C = \left[\sum_{i=1}^N C_i^{\epsilon-1/\epsilon} \right]^{\epsilon/\epsilon-1}, \epsilon > 1 \quad (17)$$

However, the problem with the AEC integration is that maximized or optimized $U(t)$ was not achieved. We examined the percentage change in the GDP and export before and after the integration, the value before was greater than the value after the integration. The ideal condition is $U(t)_{pre} < U(t)_{post}$; however, four years after the integration, empirical evidence shows that $U(t)_{pre} > U(t)_{post}$.

Peretto also presented the argument for technology and its effect after integration. Each firm produced with technology level given as:

$$X_t = X_t^{\theta} (L_{xi} - \phi) \quad (18)$$

Provided that $\phi > 0, 0 < \theta < 1$ where X_t is the firm's output and L_{xi} is the firm's labor in production, ϕ is the overhead cost, and Z_i is the firm's technology stock. The term Z^{θ} argues that labor productivity rise with accumulated stock of technology.

At equilibrium, the firm maximizes profit at:

$$V_i(t) = \int_t^{\infty} e^{-A} \prod_i(\tau) d\tau \quad (19)$$

where $A = \int_t^{\tau} r(s) ds$. The instantaneous profits are:

$$\prod_i = P_i X_i - L_{xi} - LZ_i \quad (20)$$

where L_{xi} is the total production cost, LZ_i is R&D expenditures, and V_i is the value of the firm. We do not have the data for technology transfer before or after the AEC integration. However, by inference from the Global Competitiveness Index, we note that the growth of knowledge-base in the ASEAN countries from 2015 to 2018 was not significant.

However, according to empirical evidence in this study, if the effect of the AEC integration continues to be what it has been for the past four years, the life time utility $U(t)$ would be less than what it could or should be because the condition after the integration is less than what it had been before the integration.

The basis of the argument of free trade “within the group” under economic integration is that the removal of tariffs would create more trades. At the same time the removal of tariffs will result in the loss of one source of government revenue. The gain from trade must compensate for that loss. In case of the AEC, the experience for the past four years after integration we saw a reduction in both the percentage growth of the GDP and export. To verify if the removal of tariff contributed to the loss of government revenue, we examined government revenue data in ten countries in the AEC prior to and after the integration.

6.2 The integration result in the loss of government revenue

Why the removal of tariffs did not contribute to the increase in trade? The main argument for economic integration is the expected increase in net trade that would result from the removal of tariffs. Tariffs are seen as trade barriers.

By removing trade barriers, trade volume should increase. If so, we would expect to see that the percentage of export volume will increase in a year-by-year basis. However, the pattern of percentage export for the AEC between 2015 and 2018 had steadily decreased resulting in the loss from 6.88 ± 5.29 to 5.18 ± 4.73 . The removal of trade barrier in the ASEAN countries did not contribute to the increase in net export growth.

Table 7. Government revenue during pre-AEC: 2005-2014

Year	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Brunei	45.22	47.67	32.43	63.09	38.45	43.79	55.34	46.72	46.57	37.66
Cambodia	11.95	12.78	15.13	15.89	15.81	17.05	15.58	16.93	18.52	19.85
Indonesia	17.86	18.87	17.78	19.45	15.38	15.64	17.01	17.25	16.86	16.46
Laos	12.39	13.09	13.89	14.16	14.98	20.10	20.00	21.41	21.13	20.80
Malaysia	22.01	23.30	23.65	23.85	24.81	22.46	23.85	25.04	24.12	23.66
Myanmar	10.49	10.99	10.66	10.05	9.28	9.11	9.85	19.03	20.10	21.97
Philippines	17.84	19.05	18.69	18.66	17.40	16.80	17.60	18.61	18.85	18.96
Singapore	19.91	19.76	23.79	24.00	17.38	21.08	23.14	22.21	21.39	21.19
Thailand	20.97	20.78	20.22	20.03	19.51	20.73	21.11	21.30	22.15	21.39
Vietnam	24.98	26.33	26.10	26.58	25.59	27.26	25.88	22.60	23.08	22.24
Mean	20.36	21.26	20.23	23.58	19.86	21.40	22.94	23.11	23.28	22.42
n	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
SD	9.93	10.46	6.44	14.74	8.08	9.21	12.30	8.68	8.47	5.71
T	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83
μ	14.62	15.21	16.51	15.05	15.18	16.07	15.82	18.09	18.37	19.11
σ	11.01	11.60	7.15	16.35	8.96	10.21	13.64	9.62	9.40	6.33

The mean value for government revenue in ASEAN as a percentage of the GDP for the 10 years period prior to the AEC integration was 21.84 ± 9.13 . After the integration, the government revenue as a percentage of the GDP was reduced to 19.69 ± 2.51 . Although the reduction in the government revenue is not statistically significant ($p = 0.3278$), it was enough to generate multiplicative effect to reverberate throughout the economies in the ten countries.

Fig. 5. Government revenue as percentage of the GDP for the 10 ASEAN countries.

Table 8. Government revenue during post-AEC: 2015-2018

Country	2015	2016	2017	2018
Brunei	24.15	17.61	19.53	19.46
Cambodia	18.78	19.85	19.50	19.54
Indonesia	14.88	14.33	13.98	14.18
Laos	21.13	16.23	17.02	17.31
Malaysia	22.53	20.71	19.62	19.03
Myanmar	18.73	18.82	18.23	17.44
Philippines	19.38	19.11	19.60	19.81
Singapore	21.42	20.98	23.34	20.78
Thailand	22.31	21.95	21.10	21.36
Vietnam	23.76	23.75	23.50	22.95
Mean	20.71	19.33	19.54	19.19
n	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00
SD	2.35	2.35	2.35	2.35
T	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83
μ	18.56	17.18	17.39	17.04
σ	2.61	2.61	2.61	2.61

6.3 Index of change in the GDP and export

Does the AEC integration mean mutual loss? During ten years prior to the integration, ASEAN experienced greater GDP and export growth, see Figs. 1 & 2. From 2005 to 2014, the trend of GDP growth rates for the ten countries had a group average of 5.68 ± 2.32 compared to four years after integration, the group's average percentage growth rate was 4.80 ± 2.45 . It has been a mutual loss as the result of the integration.

What is the implication of the loss in percentage growth in the GDP and export growth? Empirical evidence in this paper is antithetical to theoretical expectation of economic integration. Could it be possible that during the post-integration period, there was a downward trend of government revenue? If so, it may explain the reduction in the GDP growth. However, how can the reduction in export growth rate be explained in light of the removal of the removal of tariffs?

To provide a clearer picture of the performance evaluation of the AEC integration, we constructed indices for the GDP and export growth rate change. Using the year 2014 as the base year, we constructed an index to illustrate the performance line for the percentage change in the GDP and export growth. Both the mean percentage value of GDP and export growth rate from 2005 through 2014 was designated as 100, i.e. using the ten years mean prior to integration as the base value ending in 2014. Subsequent years: 2015, 2016, 2017 and 2018 were compared to this base year. Fig. 5 tracks the changes year-by-year from 2015 through 2018. Success means that the value should exceed 100; failure means the value is less than 100. Since the AEC integration in 2015, there has been consistent failure in percentage growth in the GDP and export volume.

Fig. 5. AEC index* of percentage GDP and export growth using ten years average prior to the integration ending in 2014 as the base value

*In constructing the index, the following steps were followed: (i) determine the ten years average from 2005 – 2014 by: $\bar{x} = (1/n) \sum x_i$, and (ii) use the observed percentage change in each year (x_i) to track the change in comparison to a fixed base-year (\bar{x}) by $I = (((x_i - \bar{x}) / \bar{x})100) + 100$.

7.0 CONCLUSION

Prior to the AEC integration, the ASEAN had diverse economic identity. Some countries enjoyed larger and faster growth, and some may be growing at a lower and slower rate. After the AEC integration, this diversity has almost been eradicated. All countries are growing uniformly at a lower and slower rate. In this assessment after four years after the integration, the ASEAN Economic Community has proved to be a failure. Unless the ASEAN states reassessed the economic effect of the AEC integration and re-aligned their policy to re-establish growth rate and speed at the pre-integration period, the entire region will suffer.

Evidence of economic integration from the OECD showed that there is a net gain from the integration. However, four years after the AEC integration, the ten countries in ASEAN experience a net loss. In this paper we examined 10 years before integration and 4 years after integration; the indicators used for the measurement were percentage change in GDP and percentage change in export. The result shows that four years after integration, there has been a net loss to the group. The 10 years pre-integration saw a mean percentage GDP growth of 5.68 ± 2.32 in the pre-integration period and 4.80 ± 2.45 in the post integration. A country-by-country examination showed that Singapore posted the greatest loss in GDP growth (-3.33); for export, Myanmar experience the greatest loss (-7.58) in percentage points. The over all significance for net gain of GDP for ASEAN is -0.27 ($p = 0.7090$ or not significant), and the group's significance for net export gain is -2.42 ($p =$

0.0047). There is no significant loss in GDP growth, but there is significant loss of export growth. The implication of this finding is that the GDP growth is less sensitive to negative effect of the integration, but the percentage growth of export is more sensitive.

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APPENDIX 1

Harod-Domar Model – Classical Growth Model

Output under Harod-Domar model depends on capital stock: $Y = f(K)$. The marginal product of capital is constant and exhibits constant rate to scale: $\frac{dY}{dK} = c \Rightarrow \frac{dY}{dK} = \frac{Y}{K}$. Capital is a necessary condition; without capital, output cannot be produced: $f(0) = 0$. These assumptions create the following condition of equal rates:

$$Y = ck \Rightarrow \log(Y) = \log(c) + \log(K)$$

$$\frac{d \log(Y)}{dt} = \frac{d \log(K)}{dt} \Rightarrow \frac{\dot{Y}}{Y} = \frac{\dot{K}}{K} \quad (\text{A1.2})$$

Further assumptions of the Harod-Domar include the assertion that savings rate and output equals investment: $sY = S = I$. Thus, the change in capital stock equals the change in investment: $\Delta K = I - \delta K$. The relationship between savings, capital, and investment may be summarized as:

$$\frac{\dot{K}}{K} = \frac{I}{K} - \delta = S \frac{Y}{K} - \delta \quad (\text{A1.2})$$

The relationship between output, savings and capital is:

$$\frac{\dot{Y}}{Y} = sc - \delta \quad (\text{A1.3})$$

The derivation of growth rate of the output follows:

$$c = \frac{dY}{dK} = \frac{Y_{t+1} - Y_t}{K_t + sY_t - dK_t - K_t}$$

$$c = \frac{Y_{t+1} - Y_t}{sY_t - \delta \frac{dK}{dY} Y_t}$$

$$c \left(sY_t - \frac{\delta dK}{dY} \right) = Y_{t+1} - Y_t \quad (\text{A1.4})$$

$$cs - c\delta \frac{dK}{dY} = \frac{Y_{t+1} - Y_t}{Y_t}$$

$$s \frac{dY}{dK} - \delta \frac{dY}{dK} \frac{dK}{dY} = \frac{Y_{t+1} - Y_t}{Y_t}$$

$$sc - \delta = \frac{\Delta Y}{Y}$$

APPENDIX 2

Solow-Swan Growth Model – Neo-Classical Exogenous Growth Model

The Solow-Swan model is two-factors production model: L(labor) and K(capital) where elasticity of substitution is asymptotically equal to one (Barelli and Pessôa, 2003; Litina and Palivos, 2008). The output equation is given by:

$$Y(t) = K(t)^a (A(t)L(t))^{1-a} \quad (\text{A2.1})$$

where t is time period and the elasticity of output is $0 < a < 1$, and $Y(t)$ is the total production. The term $A(t)$ is the labor-augmented technology or knowledge. The initial conditions are $A(0), K(0)$ and $L(0)$. Labor grows at a rate of n and capital grows at g :

$$L(t) = L(0)e^{nt} \quad (\text{A2.2})$$

$$A(t) = A(0)e^{gt} \quad (\text{A2.3})$$

The effective unit of labor: $A(t)L(t)$ grows at rates of $(n + g)$ and δ is the depreciation rate of the capital stock. The consumption amount is given by: $c = cY(t)$ with $0 < c < 1$ with savings rate of $s = 1 - c$. What is saved is used for investment: $\dot{K}(t) = \frac{dK(t)}{dt}$. The production function $Y(K, A, L)$ in per unit of labor is given by:

$$y(t) = \frac{Y(t)}{A(t)L(t)} = k(t)^a \quad (\text{A2.4})$$

The general equation for the Solow-Swan model is given by:

$$\dot{k}(t) = sk(t)^a - (n + g + \delta)k(t) \quad (\text{A2.5})$$

where $sk(t)^a = sy(t)$ is investment per unit of effective labor and $(n + g + \delta)k(t)$ is the break even point of investment (Romer, 2011). The investment at time t , $k(t)$ converges to steady-state is:

$$k^* = \left(\frac{s}{n + g + \delta} \right)^{\frac{1}{1-a}} \quad (\text{A2.6})$$

The capital stock K and labor AL are growing at a rate of $(n + g)$.

The equilibrium k^* produces:

$$\frac{K(t)}{Y(t)} = \frac{s}{n + g + \delta} \quad (\text{A2.7})$$

where $\frac{K(t)}{Y(t)} = k(t)^{1-a}$ with the marginal rate of production (MRP) as:

$$MPK = \frac{\partial Y}{\partial K} = \frac{aA^{1-a}}{(K/L)^{1-a}}$$

The ratio of income that has been appropriate for capital accumulation is a and one can equate the rate of capital accumulation to the rate of return by:

$$a = \frac{K \frac{\partial Y}{\partial K}}{Y} = \frac{rK}{Y} \quad (\text{A2.8})$$

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APPENDIX 3 Endogenous Growth Model

Economic growth is a consequence of endogenous factor (Romer, 1994). This assertion is opposite of the exogenous growth model. According to endogenous growth model, growth comes from investment in human capital, innovation, and knowledge. In this presentation of the endogenous model, we extract the argument from the work of Uzawa (1965).

The aggregate production function is given by:

$$Y(t) = F[K(t), A(t), L(t)] \tag{A3.1}$$

Technological knowledge at time t is $A(t)$. The rate of improvement in labor efficiency: $\dot{A}(t)/A(t)$ depends on the labor force, $L(t)$:

$$\frac{\dot{A}(t)}{A(t)} = \phi[L_E(t)/L(t)] \tag{A3.2}$$

The larger the improvement in labor efficiency, the higher the proportion of labor force in education sector with non increasing marginal returns:

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \phi'(s) \geq 0 \\ \phi''(s) \leq 0 \end{array} \right\} \text{for all } 0 \leq s \leq 1 \tag{A3.3}$$

The total labor force $L(t)$ at time t grows at constant rate n to be inelastically supplied:

$$\begin{aligned} L_p(t) + L_E(t) &\leq L(t) \\ L;(t)/L(t) &= n \end{aligned} \tag{A3.4}$$

Let $I(t)$ be investment, $c(t)$ be consumption, then $I(t) + c(t) \leq Y(t)$ where $I(t), c(t) \geq 0$ and the rate of capital accumulation is:

$$\frac{\dot{K}(t)}{K(t)} = I(t) - \mu K(t) \tag{A3.5}$$

where μ is the rate of capital depreciation of capital.

Let per capita output by $y = Y/L$ relate to capital-labor ratio: $k = K/L$ by the function $y = f(k)$ where $f(k) = F(K, L)/L = F(k, l)$. The function $f(k)$ is twice-differentiated: $f(k) > 0, f'(k) > 0, f''(k) < 0$ for all $k > 0$:

$$y(t) = \frac{Y(t)}{L(t)} = \text{output per capita} \tag{A3.6}$$

$$k(t) = \frac{K(t)}{L(t)} = \text{aggregate capital-labor ratio} \tag{A3.7}$$

$$u(t) = \frac{L_p(t)}{L(t)} = \text{labor allocated to productive sector} \quad (\text{A3.8})$$

$$s(t) = \frac{z(t)}{Y(t)} = \text{investment ratio} \quad (\text{A3.9})$$

According to the model, the objective is to maximize:

$$\int_0^{\infty} (1 - s(t))y(t)e^{-\delta t} dt \quad (\text{A3.10})$$

Subject to the following constraints:

$$\dot{k}(t) = s(t)y(t) - \lambda k(t) \quad (\text{A3.11})$$

$$\dot{A}(t) = A(t)\phi(1 - u(t)) \quad (\text{A3.12})$$

where $y(t) = A(t)u(t)f\left(\frac{K(t)}{A(t)u(t)}\right)$ under the condition that $0 \leq s(t), u(t) \leq 1$ where

$\delta, \lambda = n + \mu, k(0) = \frac{K(0)}{L(0)}, A(0)$ are given constants; $u(t)$ and $s(t)$ are continuous.

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APPENDIX 4

Schumpeterian Creative Destruction Growth Model

The following summary is extracted from Aghion and Howitt (1992). The Schumpeterian growth model is also called the Aghion-Howitt Model. The model argues that a monopolist has no incentive to innovate. The key to economic growth is innovation. However, for a monopolist, there is no incentive to engage in research and development to produce innovation because research requires capital investment, and the returns from such investment is less than optimum. However, in a competitive market, competition produces innovation and innovation leads to growth. Our summary of the Schumpeterian model begins with the categorization of labor.

There are three types of labor in the market, namely unskilled laborers (M) who are employed to produce consumer goods, skilled laborers (N) who are employed to produce intermediate goods, and specialized labor who are employed in research and development to produce innovation. The production function for M is given by:

$$y = AF(x) \quad (A4.1)$$

where $F' > 0$; $F'' < 0$; and y is the flow output of consumption, x is the flow of intermediate input, and A is the production function of intermediate inputs.

According to this model, intermediate goods used skilled labor to produce under linear technology function: $X = L$ where L is the flow of skilled labor in intermediate good sector.

Innovation is a random event that arrived as Poisson event: $\lambda\phi(n, R)$ where n is the flow of skilled labor in research and development, λ is a constant parameter and ϕ is the technology used in research and development. A condition where $\phi(0, R) = 0$ means if the economy allocates zero skilled labor to research and development then the economy will have zero growth.

Let time be continuous $\tau \geq 0$ where $t = 0, 1, \dots$ and the production function is given by:

$$A_t = A_0\gamma^t \quad (A4.2)$$

where A_0 is the initial value, A is productivity, and the factor of productivity $\gamma > 1$. Let x_t be the flow of intermediate good produced by a monopolist during the interval t , x_t equal to the labor employed in the manufacturing sector. The price charged by ht monopolist is:

$$p_t = A_t F'(x_t) \quad (A4.3)$$

The objective is to maximize $[A_t F'(x) - w_t]x_t$ given A_t and the wage rate w_t of skilled labor. The productivity-adjusted wage is $w_t \equiv w_t / A_t$; the marginal revenue function is $\tilde{\omega}(x) = F'(x) + xF''(x)$. If revenue is downward sloping and satisfies Inada conditions then assume that $\tilde{\omega}'(x) < 0$ for all $x > 0$, $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \tilde{\omega}(x) = \infty$, $\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{\omega}(x) = \infty$ for any output w_t and output x_t . The

condition for production is: $w_t = \tilde{\omega}(x_t)$ or $x_t = \tilde{x}(w_t)$ where \tilde{x} is the function $\tilde{\omega}^{-1}$. The monopolist profit is given by:

$$\pi_t = A_t \tilde{\pi}(w_t) \quad (A4.4)$$

where $\tilde{\pi}(w) \equiv -(\tilde{x}(w))^2 F''(\tilde{x}(w))$. According to the Cobb-Douglas production function, the consumption-good technology is $F(x) = x^a$, $0 < a < 1$ yielding the price equation for a monopolist:

$p_t = \frac{w_t}{a}$, Monopolist profit: $\pi_t = \left(\frac{1-a}{a}\right)w_t x_t$; and the monopolist output: $x_t = \left(\frac{w_t}{a^2}\right)^{\frac{1}{a-1}}$. The expected profit from research is given by:

$$\lambda\phi(z,s)V_{t+1} - w_t z - w_t^s s \tag{A4.5}$$

where V_{t+1} is innovation at time $t+0$ and w_t^s is the wage rate of specialized labor. Thus, innovation is given by:

$$V_{t+1} = \frac{\pi_{t+1}}{r + \lambda\phi(n+1)} \tag{A4.6}$$

A monopolist will not do research because $V_{t+1} - V_t < V_{t+1}$. This condition is the building block of Schumpeterian creative destruction. The next objective is to answer the question of how to allocate skilled labor N to manufacture and research:

$$\frac{\tilde{\omega}(N - n_t)}{\lambda\phi'(n_t)} \geq \frac{\gamma\tilde{\pi}(\tilde{\omega}(N - n_t))}{r + \lambda\phi(n_{t+1})}, \quad n \geq 0 \tag{A4.7}$$

Research employment at t is a function of research employment at $t+0$: $n_t = \psi(n_{t+1})$ where $\psi[0, N) \rightarrow R_+$. The marginal benefit of research is given by:

$$c(n_t) \equiv \frac{\tilde{\omega}(N - n_t)}{\lambda\phi'(n_t)} \tag{A4.8}$$

$$b(n_{t+1}) \equiv \frac{\gamma\tilde{\pi}(\tilde{\omega}(N - n_{t+1}))}{r + \lambda\phi(n_{t+1})} \tag{A4.9}$$

where $c(n_t) \rightarrow \infty$ as $n_t \rightarrow N$. The stationary equilibrium is defined as:

$$\frac{\tilde{\omega}(N - \hat{n})}{\lambda\phi'(\hat{n})} = \frac{\gamma\tilde{\pi}(\tilde{\omega}(N - \hat{n}))}{r + \lambda\phi(\hat{n})} \tag{A4.10}$$

Finally, the Average Growth Rate (AGR) and the Variance Growth Rate (VGR) are given as:

$$AVR = \lambda\phi(\hat{n}) \ln \gamma \tag{A4.11}$$

$$VGR = \lambda\phi(\hat{n})(\ln \gamma)^2 \tag{A4.12}$$

In words, the argument of the model is summarized, thus:

“...the model assumes, following Schumpeter, that individual innovations are sufficiently important to affect the entire economy. A period is the time between two successive innovations. The length of each period is random, because of the stochastic nature of the innovation process, but the relationship between the amount of research in two successive periods can be modelled as deterministic. The amount of research this period depends negatively upon the expected amount next period, through two effects.

The first effect is that of creative destruction. The payoff from research this period is the prospect of monopoly rents next period. Those rents will last only until the next innovation occurs, at which time the knowledge underlying the rents will be rendered obsolete. Thus the expected present value of the rents depends negatively upon the Poisson arrival rate of the next innovation. The expectation of more research next period will increase that arrival rate, and hence will discourage research this period.

The second effect is a general equilibrium effect working through the wage of skilled labor, which can be used either in research or in manufacturing. In order to be consistent with the conditions for labor-market equilibrium, the expectation of more research next period must correspond to an expectation of higher demand for skilled labor in research next period, which implies the expectation of a higher real wage of skilled labor. Higher wages next period will reduce the monopoly rents that can be gained by exclusive knowledge of how to produce the best products. Thus the expectation of more research next period will discourage research this period by reducing the flow of rents expected to accrue to a successful innovator.” – (Aghion and Howitt, 1992, p. 324).

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APPENDIX 5

The Big Push Theory or Rosenstein-Rodan Growth Model

Rosenstein-Rodan illustrated the concept of the Big Push Theory by presenting two factual scenario of production and spending behavior of consumers and their effect on the economy and, thus, vis-à-vis the development of the economy:

“Let us assume that 20,000 unemployed workers [...] are taken from the land and put into a large shoe factory. They receive wages substantially higher than their previous meager income in natura. [...] If these workers spent all their wages on shoes, a market for the products of their enterprise would arise [...]. The trouble is that the workers will not spend all their wages on shoes.”

...

“If, instead, one million unemployed workers were taken from the land and put, not into one industry, but into a whole series of industries which produce the bulk of the goods on which the workers would spend their wages, what was not true in the case of one shoe factory would become true in the case of a whole system of industries: it would create its own additional market, thus realising an expansion of world output with the minimum disturbance of the world markets.” - Rosenstein-Rodan, P. N. (1943). “Problems of Industrialisation of Eastern and South-Eastern Europe,” *The Economic Journal*, 53, 202–11.

The basic condition is to consider a close economy with a continuum sectors $z \in [0,1]$ and the

Cobb-Douglas utility function: $U[x(z)] = \exp \left[\int_0^1 \ln x(z) dz \right]$ where $x(z)$ is consumption of goods z .

The economy has labor $L > 0$ and wage bill of $w = 1$ and each firm has equal access to technology: $y^T(z) = l^T(z)$, each access to technology has increasing return of M in production function:

$$Y^M(z) = \max \left\{ 0, [l^M(z) - F] / \gamma \right\} \tag{A6.1}$$

where $\gamma(0,1)$. Since every firm has access to technology, there is a tendency to create multiple equilibria at:

$$1 - \gamma v > d > \frac{1 - \gamma v}{v} \tag{A6.2}$$

In order to escape this equilibria, firms needs to upgrade technology $U[x(z)] \int_0^1 u[z(z)] dz$ with

$u[x(z)] = \alpha(z) - \frac{1}{2} \beta(z)^2$; thus, the linear demand system may be constructed as:

$$p(z) \frac{\alpha - \beta x(z)}{\lambda} \tag{A6.3}$$

and $x(z) = \frac{\alpha - \lambda p(z)}{\beta} \tag{A6.4}$

$$\text{where } \lambda = \frac{\alpha \int_0^1 p(z) dz - \beta \gamma}{\int_0^1 p(z)^2 dz} \quad (\text{A6.5})$$

The following definition applied: $x(z)$ = sectoral demand; $p(z)$ = price, and Y = aggregate demand.

In explaining the Big Push Theory, Kreikermeir and Wrona summarized it in three propositions:

“*Proposition 1:* Labor condition $L \geq \bar{L}(m)$ where $\bar{L}_m \equiv \frac{m}{2[m + \sqrt{2m(1+m) + m}]}$, there are three equilibria exists: no industrialization, complete industrialization, and incomplete industrialization. For $L < \bar{L}(m)$, there is an addition a parameter range leading to multiple equilibria in which the possibilities of complete and incomplete industrialization co-exist, p. 10.

Proposition 2: Under sufficient condition ($L \in (\underline{L}(m), \bar{L}(m))$) full industrialization is welfare superior to partial industrialization and, therefore, every regime featuring multiple equilibria constitutes a poverty trap, p.13.

$$U(\bar{z}) = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ 1 - \frac{\int_0^{\bar{z}} P^M(\bar{z}) dz + \int_z^1 (\bar{z}) dz - Y(\bar{z})}{\int_0^{\bar{z}} [P^M(\bar{z})]^2 dz + \int_z^1 [P^T(\bar{z})]^2 dz} \right\}$$

Proposition 3: An economy cannot escape from poverty tram by opening up to free international trade with more partner countries.” p. 14

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APPENDIX 6 Unified Theory of Growth

The change in the labor force in any given time may be represented by:

$$L_{t+1} = n_t L_t \tag{A6.1}$$

where n_t = gross population growth rate. The quasi-linear utility function is given by:

$$u_t = m_t + \gamma \ln(n_t) \tag{A6.2}$$

where γ is the weight put on children with the individual budget constraint:

$$w_t = p_t n_t + m_t \tag{A6.2}$$

where w_t is the individual income measured by manufactured goods. The optimization problem is put by the demand for children:

$$n_t = \frac{\gamma}{P_t} \tag{A6.3}$$

Output and new technology in industry sectors are produced according to following production function:

$$Y_t^A = \mu A_t^\epsilon (L_t^A)^\alpha = A_{t+1} - A_t, \quad 0 < \alpha, \epsilon < 1 \tag{A6.4}$$

$$Y_t^M = \delta M_t^\phi L_t^M = M_{t+1} - M_t, \quad 0 < \phi < 1$$

where A_t is factor productivity in agriculture and M_t is the productivity in manufacture.

The net growth rate of a variable Z between two periods is given as:

$$g_t^z = \frac{Z_{t+1} - Z_t}{Z_t} \tag{A6.5}$$

The productivity growth in agriculture sector is:

$$g_t^A \equiv \mu A_t^{\epsilon-1} (L_t^A)^\alpha \tag{A6.6}$$

For the manufacturing sector:

$$g_t^M \equiv \mu M_t^{\phi-1} (L_t^M) \tag{A6.7}$$

At equilibrium, the total labor is given as:

$$L_t^A + L_t^M = L_t \tag{A6.8}$$

For food market equilibrium:

$$\theta_t = \frac{L_t^A}{L_t} = \left(\frac{n_t L_t^{1-\alpha}}{\mu A_t^\epsilon} \right)^{1/\alpha} \quad (\text{A6.9})$$

The relative price of food:

$$P_t = \frac{(\delta M_t^\phi)(\gamma L_t)^{1-\alpha}}{\mu A_t^\epsilon} \quad (\text{A6.10})$$

A constant growth in the agricultural sector implies that:

$$1 + g^A = (1 + g^L)^{\alpha/(1-\epsilon)} \quad (\text{A6.11})$$

For the manufacturing sector:

$$1 + g^M = (1 + g^L)^{1/(L-\phi)} \quad (\text{A6.12})$$

The population grows at a rate of:

$$1 + g_{t+1}^L = (1 + g_t^L)^\eta, \quad \eta \equiv \alpha + \frac{\alpha \epsilon}{1-\epsilon} - \frac{\phi \alpha}{1-\phi} \quad (\text{A6.13})$$

In the long run, the population will grow at a constant rate: $g_{t+1}^L = g_t^L = g^L$.

Finally, the balanced growth path is given by:

$$\epsilon < \epsilon_{crit} \equiv \frac{1 - \phi - \alpha - 2\alpha\phi}{1 - \phi + \alpha\phi} \quad (\text{A6.14})$$

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